

Supplementary table 1

List of phanerogamic species occurring in the microregion of the extreme north of Tocantins state, Bico do Papagaio, Brazil. Legend: NE = Not Evaluated, LC = Little Concern, VU = Vulnerable, CR = Critically Endangered, EN = Endangered, NT = Near Threatened, DD = Data Deficient.

Family / Species	Habit	Conservation status	Phytogeographic domain	Type of vegetation
Acanthaceae				
<i>Justicia chapadensis</i> S. Moore.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Justicia lanstyakii</i> Rizzini	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Ruellia brevifolia</i> (Pohl) C.Ezcurra	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Ruellia costata</i> (Nees) Hiern.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Ruellia geminiflora</i> Kunth	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
Alismataceae				
<i>Echinodorus paniculatus</i> Micheli	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Limnocharis laforesti</i> Duchass. ex Griseb.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Sagittaria guayanensis</i> Kunth	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Aquatic Vegetation

Alstroemeriaceae*Alstroemeria caiaponica* Ravenna

herb

NE

Cerrado

Cerrado (lato sensu)

Bomarea edulis (Tussac) Herb.

herb

NE

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado,
Mata Atlântica, Pantanal

Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

Amaranthaceae*Alternanthera brasiliana* (L.) Kuntze.

shrub

NE

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado,
Mata Atlântica, Pampa,
Pantanal

Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

Alternanthera martii R.E.Fr.

shrub

NE

Amazônia, Cerrado

Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Palm Grove

Alternanthera tenella Colla

herb

LC

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado,
Mata Atlântica, Pampa,
Pantanal

Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

Amaranthus spinosus L.

herb

NE

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado,
Mata Atlântica, Pampa

Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu)

Dysphania ambrosioides (L.) Mosyakin e
Clemants.

herb

NE

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado,
Mata Atlântica, Pampa,
Pantanal

Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga

Gomphrena agrestis Mart.

herb

LC

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado,
Mata Atlântica

Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Gomphrena celosoides</i> Mart.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Gomphrena desertorum</i> Mart.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Gomphrena hillii</i> Suess.	herb	EN	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Pfaffia gnaphaloides</i> (L.f.) Mart.	herb	LC	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre
Amaryllidaceae				
<i>Zephyranthes irwiniana</i> (Ravenna) Nic.García	herb	NE	Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu)
Anacardiaceae				
<i>Anacardium giganteum</i> W.Hancock ex Engl.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> L.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Astronium fraxinifolium</i> Schott	tree	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Astronium graveolens</i> Jacq.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area
<i>Spondias mombin</i> L.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest

<i>Tapirira guianensis</i> Aubl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Annonaceae				
<i>Annona coriacea</i> Mart.	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Annona crassiflora</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Annona exsucca</i> DC.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Annona montana</i> Macfad.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Annona paludosa</i> Aubl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Annona sericea</i> Dunal	tree	LC	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest
<i>Bocageopsis mattogrossensis</i> (R.E.Fr.) R.E.Fr.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Duguetia marcgraviana</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Guatteria citriodora</i> Ducke	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Guatteria schomburgkiana</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Guatteria sellowiana</i> Schltldl.	tree	LC	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Oxandra reticulata</i> Maas	shrub	LC	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest

<i>Unonopsis guatterioides</i> (A.DC.) R.E.Fr.	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Xylopia aromatica</i> (Lam.) Mart.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Xylopia sericea</i> A.St.-Hil.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Apocynaceae				
<i>Asclepias curassavica</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga
<i>Asclepias mellodora</i> A.St.-Hil.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Aspidosperma cuspa</i> (Kunth) Blake	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Aspidosperma desmanthum</i> Benth. ex Müll.Arg.	tree	LC	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest
<i>Aspidosperma macrocarpon</i> Mart. & Zucc.	tree	LC	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Aspidosperma melanocalyx</i> Müll.Arg.	tree	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest

<i>Aspidosperma subincanum</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Blepharodon pictum</i> (Vahl) W.D.Stevens	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Ditassa hastata</i> Decne.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Geissospermum sericeum</i> Miers	tree	NE	Amazônia	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Hancornia speciosa</i> Gomes	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Himatanthus articulatus</i> (Vahl) Woodson	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Himatanthus bracteatus</i> (A.DC.) Woodson	tree	NE	Mata Atlântica	Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Himatanthus drasticus</i> (Mart.) Plumel	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Himatanthus obovatus</i> (Müll.Arg.) Woodson	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Mandevilla hirsuta</i> (A.Rich.) K.Schum.	climber	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Mandevilla scabra</i> (Hoffmanns. ex Roem. & Schult.) K.Schum.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Matelea pedalis</i> (E.Fourn.) Fontella & E.A.Schwarz	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Odontadenia nitida</i> (Vahl) Müll.Arg.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna

<i>Rhodocalyx rotundifolius</i> Müll. Arg.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Schubertia grandiflora</i> Mart.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Tassadia propinqua</i> Decne.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Aptandraceae				
<i>Cathedra acuminata</i> (Benth.) Miers	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest
<i>Cathedra paraensis</i> Sleumer	tree	NE	Amazônia	Campinarana, Terra Firme Forest
Aquifoliaceae				
<i>Ilex affinis</i> Gardner	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Araceae				
<i>Anthurium pentaphyllum</i> (Aubl.) G.Don	herb	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Urospatha sagittifolia</i> (Rudge) Schott	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Palm Grove
Araliaceae				
<i>Didymopanax morototoni</i> (Aubl.) Decne. & Planch.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
Arecaceae				
<i>Acrocomia aculeata</i> (Jacq.) Lodd. ex Mart.	tree	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest

<i>Allagoptera campestris</i> (Mart.) Kuntze.	palm	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Allagoptera leucocalyx</i> (Drude) Kuntze.	palm	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Astrocaryum campestre</i> Mart.	palm	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Astrocaryum vulgare</i> Mart.	palm	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Attalea eichleri</i> (Drude) A.J.Hend.	palm	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Attalea maripa</i> (Aubl.) Mart.	herb	NE	Amazônia	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Attalea speciosa</i> Mart. ex Spreng.	palm	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove
<i>Desmoncus horridus</i> subsp. <i>horridus</i> Splitg. ex Mart.	palm	NE	Amazônia	Igapó Forest
<i>Desmoncus polyacanthos</i> Mart.	palm	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Euterpe precatoria</i> Mart.	palm	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Mauritia flexuosa</i> L.f.	palm	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Palm Grove
<i>Mauritiella armata</i> (Mart.) Burret.	palm	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Oenocarpus distichus</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Syagrus cocoides</i> Mart.	palm	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Syagrus comosa</i> (Mart.) Mart.	palm	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Aristolochiaceae				
<i>Aristolochia clausenii</i> Duch.	climber	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Aristolochia esperanzae</i> Kuntze.	climber	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Aristolochia stomachoides</i> Hoehne	herb	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Aristolochia urupaensis</i> Hoehne.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
Asteraceae				
<i>Blainvillea acmella</i> (L.) Philipson	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Chromolaena ferruginea</i> (Gardner) R.M.King & H.Rob.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (L.) R.M.King & H.Rob.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Chromolaena squalida</i> (DC.) R.M.King & H.Rob.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Cosmos caudatus</i> Kunth	herb	NE	Cerrado	Anthropic Area
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Elaphandra ulei</i> (Hieron.) H.Rob.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Elephantopus hirtiflorus</i> DC.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga
<i>Eleutheranthera ruderalis</i> (Sw.) Sch.Bip	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area
<i>Erechtites hieracifolius</i> (L.) Raf. ex DC.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna

<i>Heterocondylus vitalbae</i> (DC.) R.M.King & H.Rob.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Lepidaploa aurea</i> (Mart. ex DC.) H. Robinson	shrub	LC	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Lepidaploa muricata</i> (DC.) H.Rob.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Lepidaploa remotiflora</i> (Rich.) H.Rob.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre
<i>Mochiniastrum barrosoae</i> Cabrera	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Pectis elongata</i> Kunth	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Praxelis diffusa</i> (Rich.) Pruski	herb	NE	Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Riencourtia latifolia</i> Gardner.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Riencourtia pedunculosa</i> (Rich.) Pruski.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Staurochlamys burchellii</i> Baker	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Synedrella nodiflora</i> (L.) Gaertn.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Tilesia baccata</i> (L.) Pruski	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga
<i>Trichogonia salviifolia</i> Gardner	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Vernonanthura brasiliiana</i> (L.) H.Rob.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
Begoniaceae				

<i>Begonia humilis</i> Aiton.	herb	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest
Bignoniaceae				
<i>Adenocalymma peregrinum</i> (Miers) L.G.Lohmann	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Amphilophium paniculatum</i> (L.) Kunth	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Carrasco, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Cuspidaria bracteolata</i> (DC.) Kaehler & L.G.Lohmann	climber	NE	Amazônia	Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Cuspidaria lateriflora</i> (Mart.) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest
<i>Cybistax antisyphilitica</i> (Mart.) Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest
<i>Dolichandra quadrivalvis</i> (Jacq.) L.G.Lohmann	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Fridericia cinnamomea</i> (DC.) L.G.Lohmann	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Fridericia dispar</i> (Bureau ex K.Schum.) L.G.Lohmann	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Fridericia florida</i> (DC.) L.G.Lohmann	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Fridericia platyphylla</i> (Cham.) L.G.Lohmann	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Fridericia samydoides</i> (Cham.) L.G.Lohmann.	climber	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Handroanthus chrysotrichus</i> (Mart. ex DC.) Mattos	tree	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Handroanthus impetiginosus</i> (Mart. ex DC.) Mattos	tree	NT	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Handroanthus ochraceus</i> (Cham.) Mattos	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Jacaranda brasiliana</i> (Lam.) Pers.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Jacaranda rufa</i> Silva Manso	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Stizophyllum perforatum</i> (Cham.) Miers	climber	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Tabebuia aurea</i> (Silva Manso) Benth. & Hook.f. ex S.Moore	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Tabebuia insignis</i> (Miq.) Sandwith	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campo de Várzea, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Restinga

<i>Tabebuia roseoalba</i> (Ridl.) Sandwith	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Juss. ex Kunth	tree	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Zeyheria montana</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Bixaceae				
<i>Bixa orellana</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Cochlospermum regium</i> (Mart. ex Schrank) Pilg.	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
Blechnaceae				
<i>Telmatoblechnum serrulatum</i> (Rich.) Perrie, D.J. Ohlsen & Brownsey	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga
Boraginaceae				
<i>Cordia ecalyculata</i> Vell.	tree	NE	Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest
<i>Cordia glabrata</i> (Mart.) A.DC.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Cordia nodosa</i> Lam.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Cordia rufescens</i> A.DC.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Cordia sellowiana</i> Cham.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Cordia superba</i> Cham.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Euploca pallescens</i> (I.M.Johnst.) J.I.M.Melo & Semir.	herb	NE	Cerrado, Pantanal	Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Varronia multispicata</i> (Cham.) Borhidi.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Varronia spinescens</i> (L.) Borhidi.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
Bromeliaceae				
<i>Aechmea castelnavii</i> Baker	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo de Várzea, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Palm Grove, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Aechmea tocantina</i> Baker	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Ananas ananassoides</i> (Baker) L.B.Sm.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Bromelia sylvicola</i> S.Moore	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Pitcairnia crinita</i> E.Pereira & Martinelli.	herb	NE	Amazônia	Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Pitcairnia ensifolia</i> Nez	herb	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
Burmanniaceae				

<i>Burmannia flava</i> Mart.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
Burseraceae				
<i>Protium altissimum</i> (Aubl.) Marchand	tree	NE	Amazônia	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Protium heptaphyllum</i> (Aubl.) Marchand	tree	DD	Amazônia	Campinarana, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Protium rhynchophyllum</i> (Rusby) Daly & P.Fine	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Protium spruceanum</i> (Benth.) Engl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Protium unifoliolatum</i> Engl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Cabombaceae				
<i>Cabomba furcata</i> Schult. & Schult.f.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Aquatic Vegetation
Cannabaceae				
<i>Celtis iguanaea</i> (Jacq.) Sarg.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Trema micrantha</i> (L.) Blume	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Capparaceae				
<i>Cynophalla flexuosa</i> (L.) J.Presl	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga

<i>Mesocapparis lineata</i> (Dombey ex Pers.) Cornejo & Iltis	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga
Caryocaraceae				
<i>Caryocar cuneatum</i> Wittm.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Polycarpaea corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Spergula arvensis</i> L.	herb	NE	Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo
Celastraceae				
<i>Cheiloclinium cognatum</i> (Miers) A.C.Sm.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Hippocratea volubilis</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Carrasco, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Manguezal, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Chrysobalanaceae				
<i>Couepia grandiflora</i> (Mart. & Zucc.) Benth.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Couepia uiti</i> (Mart. & Zucc.) Benth. ex Hook.f.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Exellodendron cordatum</i> (Hook.f.) Prance	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Hirtella ciliata</i> Mart. & Zucc.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Hirtella glandulosa</i> Spreng.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Restinga
<i>Hirtella gracilipes</i> (Hook.f.) Prance	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Hirtella racemosa</i> Lam.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Leptobalanus apetalus</i> (E.Mey.) Sothers & Prance	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Leptobalanus gardneri</i> (Hook.f.) Sothers & Prance.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Leptobalanus sclerophyllus</i> (Hook.f.) Sothers & Prance.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest
<i>Licania kunthiana</i> Hook.f.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Cleomaceae				
<i>Physostemon guianense</i> (Aubl.) Malme	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Riparian Forest, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Tarenaya aculeata</i> (L.) Soares Neto & Roalson	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous

				Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Aquatic Vegetation, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Clusiaceae				
<i>Calophyllum brasiliense</i> Cambess	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove, Restinga
<i>Caraipa densifolia</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Clusia weddeliana</i> Planch. & Triana	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest
<i>Garcinia madruno</i> (Kunth) Hammel	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Kielmeyera speciosa</i> A.St.-Hil.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Platonia insignis</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Combretaceae				
<i>Combretum fruticosum</i> (Loefl.) Stuntz	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Combretum laxum</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Combretum leprosum</i> Mart.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Combretum mellifluum</i> Eichler	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Terminalia corrugata</i> (Ducke) Gere & Boatwr.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Terminalia fagifolia</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Terminalia lucida</i> Hoffmanns. ex Mart. & Zucc.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Varzea Forest
Commelinaceae				
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Murdannia nudiflora</i> (L.) Brenan	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
Connaraceae				
<i>Bernardinia fluminensis</i> (Gardner) Planch.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Connarus suberosus</i> Planch.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Rourea doniana</i> Baker	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Carrasco, Igapó Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
Convolvulaceae				

<i>Camonea umbellata</i> (L.) A.R. Simões & Staples	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Distimake aegyptius</i> (L.) A.R. Simões & Staples	climber	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Distimake macrocalyx</i> (Ruiz & Pav.) A.R. Simões & Staples	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga
<i>Evolvulus filipes</i> Mart.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Evolvulus niveus</i> Mart.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Evolvulus nummularius</i> (L.) L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Ipomoea bahiensis</i> Willd. ex Roem. & Schult.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Ipomoea batatoides</i> Choisy	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Ipomoea burchellii</i> Meisn.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Ipomoea carajasensis</i> D.F.Austin	climber	VU	Amazônia, Cerrado, Pantanal	Campinarana, Campo Limpo
<i>Ipomoea decora</i> Meisn.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Amazonian Savanna

<i>Ipomoea mauritiana</i> Jacq.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Mata Atlântica	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Ipomoea nil</i> (L.) Roth	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest
<i>Ipomoea philomega</i> (Vell.) House	climber	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Ipomoea rubens</i> Choisy	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Ipomoea saopaulista</i> O'Donnell	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Ipomoea setifera</i> Poir.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Restinga
<i>Jacquemontia gracilis</i> Choisy.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Jacquemontia gracillima</i> (Choisy) Hallier f.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Jacquemontia spiciflora</i> (Choisy) Hallier f.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Jacquemontia tamnifolia</i> (L.) Griseb.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Maripa reticulata</i> Ducke	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Amazonian Savanna

<i>Operculina hamiltonii</i> (G.Don) D.F.Austin & Staples.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
Costaceae				
<i>Costus spiralis</i> (Jacq.) Roscoe	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
Cucurbitaceae				
<i>Melothria pendula</i> L	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Cyperaceae				
<i>Abildgaardia ovata</i> (Burm.f.) Kral	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Bulbostylis capillaris</i> (L.) C.B.Clarke	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Bulbostylis conifera</i> (Kunth) C.B.Clarke.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Bulbostylis junciformis</i> (Kunth) C.B. Clarke	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Calyptrocarya luzuliformis</i> T.Koyama	herb	NE	Amazônia	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Palm Grove

<i>Calyptracarya poeppigiana</i> Kunth.	herb	NE	Amazônia	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Cyperus amabilis</i> Vahl	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Cyperus compressus</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Cyperus distans</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Restinga
<i>Cyperus haspan</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Riparian Forest, Manguezal, Palm Grove, Restinga, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Cyperus laxus</i> Lam.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest
<i>Cyperus ligularis</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Riparian Forest, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Cyperus luzulae</i> (L.) Retz.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Aquatic Vegetation, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Cyperus schomburgkianus</i> Nees	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Aquatic Vegetation, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

<i>Cyperus surinamensis</i> Rottb.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Diplacrum guianense</i> (Nees) T.Koyama	herb	NE	Amazônia	Anthropic Area, Terra Firme Forest, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Eleocharis interstincta</i> (Vahl) Roem. ex Schult.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Varzea Forest, Restinga, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> (L.) Vahl	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Manguezal, Palm Grove, Restinga
<i>Fimbristylis littoralis</i> Gaudich.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Restinga, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Lagenocarpus verticillatus</i> (Spreng.) T.Koyama & Maguire.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Rhynchospora barbata</i> (Vahl) Kunth.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Rhynchospora cephalotes</i> (L.) Vahl	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest
<i>Rhynchospora comata</i> (Link) Roem. & Schult.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Rhynchospora consanguinea</i> (Kunth) Boeckeler.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Rhynchospora nervosa</i> (Vahl) Boeckeler	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest
<i>Rhynchospora trichochaeta</i> C.B.Clarke.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Scleria arguta</i> (Nees) Steud.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Scleria gaertneri</i> Raddi	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Dichapetalaceae				
<i>Tapura amazonica</i> Poepp. & Endl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest
Dilleniaceae				
<i>Curatella americana</i> L.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Davilla cearensis</i> Huber	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga
<i>Davilla nitida</i> (Vahl) Kubitzki	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Davilla rugosa</i> Poir.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Doliocarpus brevipedicellatus</i> Garcke	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna

<i>Doliocarpus major</i> J.F.Gmel.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Dioscoreaceae				
<i>Dioscorea alata</i> L.	climber	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area
<i>Dioscorea multiflora</i> Mart. ex Griseb.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Dioscorea orthogoneura</i> Uline ex Hochr.	climber	LC	Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Dioscorea trifida</i> L.f.	climber	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
Ebenaceae				
<i>Diospyros inconstans</i> subsp. <i>obovata</i> (Mart. ex Miq.) B.Walln.	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Diospyros lasiocalyx</i> (Mart.) B.Walln.	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Diospyros poeppigiana</i> A.DC.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Campinarana, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Diospyros sericea</i> A.DC.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Elaeocarpaceae				
<i>Sloanea robusta</i> Uittien.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest
<i>Sloanea sinemariensis</i> Aubl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest

Eriocaulaceae*Paepalanthus subtilis* Miq.

herb

NE

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado

Campinarana, Campo Rupestre

Syngonanthus gracilis (Bong.) Ruhland

herb

NE

Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata
Atlântica

Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre

Erythropalaceae*Heisteria acuminata* (Humb. & Bonpl.) Engl.

tree

NE

Amazônia

Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest
(Rainforest)*Heisteria ovata* Benth.

shrub

NE

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado,
Mata AtlânticaCaatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu),
Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest**Erythroxylaceae***Erythroxylum barbatum* O.E.Schulz

shrub

NE

Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado,
Mata AtlânticaCaatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu),
Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest,
Restinga*Erythroxylum campestre* A.St.-Hil

shrub

NE

Cerrado, Mata Atlântica

Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)

Erythroxylum deciduum A.St.-Hil.

shrub

NE

Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata
AtlânticaCerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal
Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)*Erythroxylum macrophyllum* Cav.

tree

NE

Cerrado, Mata Atlântica

Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo
Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal
Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest),
Rocky Outcrop Vegetation*Erythroxylum pelleterianum* A.St.-Hil.

tree

LC

Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata
AtlânticaCerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous
Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest*Erythroxylum pruinatum* O. E. Schulz.

tree

NE

Amazônia, Cerrado

Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna

Erythroxylum squamatum Sw.

tree

NE

Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata
AtlânticaCerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous
Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Erythroxylum suberosum</i> A.St.-Hil.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Erythroxylum subracemosum</i> Turcz.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Erythroxylum umbu</i> Costa-Lima.	shrub	NE	Mata Atlântica	Altitude Field, Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga
<i>Erythroxylum vacciniifolium</i> Mart.	shrub	NE	Caatinga	Campo Rupestre, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Euphorbiaceae				
<i>Acalypha alopecuroidea</i> Jacq.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Acalypha communis</i> Müll.Arg.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Acalypha villosa</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Alchornea castaneifolia</i> (Willd.) A.Juss.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest
<i>Caperonia castaneifolia</i> (L.) A. St.-Hil.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Restinga, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Cnidocolus vitifolius</i> (Mill.) Pohl	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Croton adenocalyx</i> Baill.	shrub	NE	Caatinga	Caatinga (stricto sensu)
<i>Croton glandulosus</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous

				Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Manguezal, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Croton hirtus</i> L Hér.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Croton lundianus</i> (Didr.) Müll.Arg.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Croton pedicellatus</i> Kunth	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Croton polyandrus</i> Spreng.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Mata Atlântica	Restinga
<i>Croton trinitatis</i> Millsp.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Riparian Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Croton urucurana</i> Baill.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Dalechampia pernambucensis</i> Baill.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Dalechampia tiliifolia</i> Lam.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Dalechampia triphylla</i> Lam.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Mata Atlântica	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga	Anthropic Area
<i>Euphorbia hyssopifolia</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area

<i>Jatropha elliptica</i> (Pohl) Oken	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Palm Grove
<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Mabea angustifolia</i> Spruce ex Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Mabea fistulifera</i> Mart.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Mabea paniculata</i> Spruce ex Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Mabea piriri</i> Aubl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo de Várzea, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Mabea pohliana</i> (Benth.) Müll. Arg.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Manihot anomala</i> Pohl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Manihot caerulescens</i> Pohl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Manihot esculenta</i> Crantz	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga

<i>Manihot leptopoda</i> (Müll.Arg.) D.J.Rogers & Appan	shrub	NE	Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Manihot maracasensis</i> Ule	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Manihot pohlii</i> Wawra.	shrub	NE	Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Manihot quinquepartita</i> Huber ex D.J.Rogers & Appan	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Manihot tripartita</i> (Spreng.) Müll.Arg.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Microstachys corniculata</i> (Vahl) Griseb.	shrub	NE	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Microstachys daphnoides</i> (Mart. & Zucc.) F.Dietr.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Microstachys hispida</i> (Mart. & Zucc.) F.Dietr.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Microstachys salicifolia</i> (Mart.) [Pscheidt & Cordeiro ex] M.J.Silva	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
Fabaceae				
<i>Abarema cochleata</i> (Willd.) Barneby & J.W.Grimes.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Aeschynomene americana</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest),

<i>Aeschynomene ciliata</i> Vogel.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Amazonian Savanna, Aquatic Vegetation, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Aeschynomene evenia</i>	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Andira cujabensis</i> Benth.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Andira vermifuga</i> (Mart.) Benth.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Apuleia leiocarpa</i> (Vogel) J.F.Macbr.	shrub	VU	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Arachis burchellii</i> Krapov. & W.C.Greg.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Arachis macedoi</i> Krapov. & W.C.Greg.	herb	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Arachis prostrata</i> Benth.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Arachis pusilla</i> Benth.	herb	NE	Caatinga	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest

<i>Arachis veigae</i> S.H.Santana & Valls	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Ateleia guaraya</i> Herzog	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Bauhinia acuruana</i> Moric.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Bauhinia bombaciflora</i> Ducke.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Bauhinia curvula</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Bauhinia dubia</i> G.Don.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Bauhinia lamprophylla</i> Harms.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Bauhinia membranacea</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Bauhinia mollis</i> (Bong.) D.Dietr.	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Bauhinia pentandra</i> (Bong.) D.Dietr.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Bauhinia platypetala</i> Burch. ex Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Palm Grove
<i>Bauhinia rufa</i> (Bong.) Steud.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Bauhinia unguolata</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Calopogonium mucunoides</i> Desv.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna

<i>Calopogonium velutinum</i> (Benth.) Amshoff	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Campsiandra angustifolia</i> Spruce ex Benth.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Campsiandra laurifolia</i> Benth.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Igapó Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Canavalia grandiflora</i> Benth.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Palm Grove
<i>Cenostigma bracteosum</i> (Tul.) Gagnon & G.P.Lewis	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Cenostigma macrophyllum</i> Tul.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Centrosema angustifolium</i> (Kunth) Benth.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Centrosema bifidum</i> Benth.	climber	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Centrosema macrocarpum</i> Benth.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Centrosema platycarpum</i> Benth	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Centrosema plumieri</i> (Turpin ex Pers.) Benth.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Centrosema rotundifolium</i> Mart. ex Benth.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Centrosema tapirapoanense</i> Hoehne	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Centrosema venosum</i> Mart. ex Benth.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Cerradicola elliptica</i> (Desv) L.P.Queiroz	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Chamaecrista bahiae</i> (H.S.Irwin) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	tree	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Chamaecrista desvauxii</i> (Collad.) Killip.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Chamaecrista ensiformis</i> (Vell.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Chamaecrista flexuosa</i> (L.) Greene.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Chamaecrista juruenensis</i> (Hoehne) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Chamaecrista linearis</i> (H.S.Irwin & Barneby) Afr.Fern. & E.P.Nunes	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Chamaecrista nictitans</i> (L.) Moench	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest,

<i>Chamaecrista ramosa</i> (Vogel) H.S. Irwin & Barneby	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Chamaecrista rotundifolia</i> (Pers.) Greene.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Chamaecrista trichopoda</i> (Benth.) Britton & Rose ex Britton & Killip.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Chamaecrista viscosa</i> (Kunth) H.S. Irwin & Barneby	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Clitoria fairchildiana</i> R.A. Howard	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Manguezal, Restinga
<i>Clitoria falcata</i> Lam.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Clitoria simplicifolia</i> (Kunth) Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Copaifera langsdorffii</i> Desf.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Copaifera marginata</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Copaifera martii</i> Hayne	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Cratylia argentea</i> (Desv.) Kuntze	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Crotalaria lanceolata</i> E.Mey.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Crotalaria pallida</i> Aiton.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Crotalaria pilosa</i> Mill.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Ctenodon histrix</i> (Poir.) D.B.O.S.Cardoso, P.L.R.Moraes & H.C.Lima	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Ctenodon paniculatus</i> (Willd. ex Vogel) D.B.O.S.Cardoso, P.L.R.Moraes & H.C.Lima	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga
<i>Dalbergia frutescens</i> (Vell.) Britton	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Deguelia densiflora</i> (Benth.) A.M.G.Azevedo ex M.Sousa	climber	NE	Amazônia	Anthropic Area, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Deguelia nitidula</i> (Benth.) A.M.G.Azevedo & R.A.Camargo	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna

<i>Desmodium barbatum</i> (L.) Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Dialium guianense</i> (Aubl.) Sandwith	tree	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Dimorphandra gardneriana</i> Tul.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Dimorphandra mollis</i> Benth.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Pantanal	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Dioclea virgata</i> (Rich.) Amshoff	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Manguezal, Restinga
<i>Enterolobium contortisiliquum</i> (Vell.) Morong	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Enterolobium gummiferum</i> (Mart.) J.F.Macbr.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Eriosema congestum</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Eriosema longiflorum</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Eriosema violaceum</i> (Aubl.) G.Don.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Amazonian Savanna
<i>Galactia jussiaeana</i> Kunth	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna

<i>Hymenaea courbaril</i> L.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Hymenaea rubriflora</i> Ducke	shrub	NE	Mata Atlântica	Restinga
<i>Hymenaea stigonocarpa</i> Mart. ex Hayne	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Indigofera lespedezioides</i> Kunth	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Indigofera suffruticosa</i> Mill.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Inga heterophylla</i> Willd.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Inga ingoides</i> (Rich.) Willd.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Inga vera</i> Willd.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Leptolobium dasycarpum</i> Vogel.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Leptolobium nitens</i> Vogel	tree	NE	Amazônia	Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest
<i>Libidibia ferrea</i> (Mart. ex Tul.) L.P.Queiroz	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Lonchocarpus sericeus</i> (Poir.) Kunth ex A.DC.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Machaerium aculeatum</i> Raddi	climber	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Machaerium acutifolium</i> Vogel.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Macropsychanthus bicolor</i> (Benth.) L.P. Queiroz & Snak.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Macroptilium gracile</i> (Poepp. ex Benth.) Urb.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga
<i>Macroptilium lathyroides</i> (L.) Urb.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Martiodendron mediterraneum</i> (Mart. ex Benth.) Koeppen	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Mimosa caesalpinifolia</i> Benth.	shrub	LC	Caatinga	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Mimosa debilis</i> Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Palm Grove, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Mimosa diplotricha</i> C. Wright ex Sauvalle	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Mimosa skinneri</i> Benth.	herb	CR	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Mimosa somnians</i> Hum. & Bonpl. ex Willd.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Mimosa xanthocentra</i> Mart.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area
<i>Mucuna sloanei</i> Fawc. & Rendle	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest
<i>Parapiptadenia zehntneri</i> (Harms) M.P.M. de Lima & H.C. de Lima	tree	NE	Caatinga	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Parkia platycephala</i> Benth.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Periandra coccinea</i> (Schrad.) Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Periandra heterophylla</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Plathymenia reticulata</i> Benth.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Platypodium elegans</i> Vogel	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Pterocarpus rohrii</i> Vahl.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Rhynchosia melanocarpa</i> Grear	climber	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Samanea tubulosa</i> (Benth.) Barneby & J.W.Grimes	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Schnella glabra</i> (Jacq.) Dugand	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove
<i>Schnella outimouta</i> (Aubl.) Wunderlin.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Senegalia polyphylla</i> (DC.) Britton & Rose	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Senegalia riparia</i> (Kunth) Britton & Killip	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Senna alata</i> (L.) Roxb.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga
<i>Senna latifolia</i> (G.Mey.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest

<i>Senna mucronifera</i> (Mart. ex Benth.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Senna multijuga</i> (Rich.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Senna pendula</i> (Humb.& Bonpl.ex Willd.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Senna silvestris</i> (Vell.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Soemmeringia semperflorens</i> Mart.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Stryphnodendron guianense</i> (Aubl.) Benth.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Stryphnodendron rotundifolium</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Stylosanthes angustifolia</i> Vogel	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Stylosanthes capitata</i> Vogel	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest

<i>Stylosanthes gracilis</i> Kunth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Stylosanthes guianensis</i> (Aubl.) Sw.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Stylosanthes scabra</i> Vogel	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Swartzia acutifolia</i> Vogel.	tree	LC	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Swartzia arumateuana</i> (R.S. Cowan) Torke & Mansano	tree	NE	Amazônia	Campo de Várzea
<i>Swartzia flaemingii</i> Raddi	tree	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Mata Atlântica	Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Swartzia parvipetala</i> (R.S.Cowan) Mansano	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Tachigali aurea</i> Tul.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Tachigali subvelutina</i> (Benth.) Oliveira-Filho	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Tachigali vulgaris</i> L.G.Silva & H.C.Lima	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Tephrosia domingensis</i> (Willd.) Pers.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Vachellia farnesiana</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest,

<i>Vatairea macrocarpa</i> (Benth.) Ducke	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Zornia latifolia</i> Sm.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Anthropogenic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Zornia reticulata</i> Sm.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropogenic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
Gentianaceae				
<i>Chelonanthus alatus</i> (Aubl.) Pulle	herb	NE	Amazônia	Campinarana, Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Chelonanthus viridiflorus</i> (Mart.) Gilg.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Igapó Forest
<i>Coutoubea spicata</i> Aubl.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropogenic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Curtia tenuifolia</i> (Aubl.) Knobl.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
Gesneriaceae				
<i>Drymonia serrulata</i> (Jacq.) Mart.	climber	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Goyazia rupicola</i> Taub.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Mandirola multiflora</i> (Gardner) Decne.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Mandirola rupestris</i> (Gardner) Roalson & Boggan.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

Haemodoraceae				
<i>Schiekia orinocensis</i> (Kunth.) Meisn.	herb	NE	Amazônia	Igapó Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Heliconiaceae				
<i>Heliconia psittacorum</i> L.f.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Humiriaceae				
<i>Humiria balsamifera</i> (Aubl.) St.-Hil	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Sacoglottis guianensis</i> Benth.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
Hydroleaceae				
<i>Hydrolea spinosa</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna, Aquatic Vegetation
Hypericaceae				
<i>Vismia cayennensis</i> (Jacq.) Pers.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana
<i>Vismia guianensis</i> (Aubl.) Choisy.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Vismia macrophylla</i> Kunth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Vismia tenuinervia</i> (M.E. Berg) N. Robson	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest

Hypoxidaceae				
<i>Curculigo scorzonnerifolia</i> (Lam.) Baker.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Icacinaceae				
<i>Emmotum nitens</i> (Benth.) Miers	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
Iridaceae				
<i>Cipura paludosa</i> Aubl.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Cipura xanthomelas</i> Klatt.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Krameriaceae				
<i>Krameria grandiflora</i> A.St.-Hil.	herb	LC	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Krameria tomentosa</i> A. St.-Hil	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
Lamiaceae				
<i>Amasonia angustifolia</i> Mart.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre
<i>Amasonia arborea</i> Kunth	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga
<i>Amasonia campestris</i> (Aubl.) Moldenke	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Amasonia hirta</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Amasonia obovata</i> Gleason	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest

<i>Eriopidion strictum</i> (Benth.) Harley	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Hyptis atrorubens</i> Poit.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Hyptis crenata</i> Pohl ex Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Palm Grove, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Hyptis lanceolata</i> Poir.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Hyptis lutescens</i> Pohl ex Benth.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Marsypianthes chamaedrys</i> (Vahl) Kuntze.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Mesosphaerum suaveolens</i> (L.) Kuntze	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga
<i>Ocimum transamazonicum</i> C.Pereira	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Vitex capitata</i> Vahl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga
<i>Vitex panshiniana</i> Moldenke	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Vitex triflora</i> Vahl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
Lauraceae				
<i>Aniba heringeri</i> Vattimo-Gil.	shrub	LC	Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Nectandra cuspidata</i> Nees	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Nectandra gardneri</i> Meisn.	tree	NE	Cerrado, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Nectandra reticulata</i> (Ruiz & Pav.) Mez	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga
<i>Nectandra turbacensis</i> (Kunth) Nees	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Ocotea diospyrifolia</i> (Meisn.) Mez	tree	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Cerrado (lato sensu), Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Lecythidaceae				
<i>Cariniana domestica</i> (Mart.) Miers	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Terra Firme Forest
<i>Cariniana rubra</i> Gardner ex Miers.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Eschweilera albiflora</i> (DC.) Miers	tree	NE	Amazônia	Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Eschweilera ovata</i> (Cambess.) Mart. ex Miers	tree	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga

<i>Gustavia augusta</i> L.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Lecythis pisonis</i> Cambess.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Lentibulariaceae				
<i>Gymnosiphon cymosus</i> (Benth.) Benth. & Hook.f.	herb	NE	Amazônia	Campinarana, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Utricularia subulata</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove, Restinga, Aquatic Vegetation, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Loganiaceae				
<i>Antonia ovata</i> Pohl	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Spigelia anthelmia</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Restinga
<i>Strychnos pseudoquina</i> A.St.-Hil.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Loranthaceae				
<i>Passovia pedunculata</i> (Jacq.) Kuijt	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Psittacanthus biternatus</i> (Hoffmanns.) G.Don.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Restinga

<i>Psittacanthus cucullaris</i> (Lam.) G.Don	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
Lythraceae				
<i>Cuphea antisiphilitica</i> Kunth	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Cuphea micrantha</i> Kunth.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Cuphea spermacoce</i> var. <i>erectifolia</i> (Koehe) T.B.Cavalc. & S.A.Graham	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Cuphea tenuissima</i> Koehe	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Diplusodon virgatus</i> Pohl.	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Lafoensia pacari</i> A.St.-Hil.	tree	LC	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
Malpighiaceae				
<i>Alicia anisopetala</i> (A.Juss.) W.R.Anderson	climber	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Aenigmatanthera lasiandra</i> (A.Juss.) W.R.Anderson.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Banisteriopsis gardneriana</i> (A. Juss.) W.R. Anderson & B. Gates	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Banisteriopsis oxyclada</i> (A.Juss.) B.Gates	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Banisteriopsis schizoptera</i> (A.Juss.) B.Gates	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Banisteriopsis stellaris</i> (Griseb.) B. Gates	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Byrsonima coccolobifolia</i> Kunth.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Amazonian Savanna

<i>Byrsonima crassifolia</i> (L.) Kunth	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Byrsonima cydoniifolia</i> A.Juss.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Byrsonima pachyphylla</i> A. Juss.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Byrsonima verbascifolia</i> (L.) DC.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Galphimia australis</i> Chodat	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Glicophyllum jussieuanum</i> (Nied.) R.F.Almeida	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Pterandra andersonii</i> C.E.Anderson	shrub	DD	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Tetrapterys discolor</i> (G.Mey.) DC.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Malvaceae				
<i>Apeiba tibourbou</i> Aubl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Corchorus aestuans</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Corchorus hirtus</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Corchorus olitorius</i> L.	shrub	NE	Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Guazuma ulmifolia</i> Lam.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest

<i>Helicteres andersonii</i> Cristóbal.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Helicteres brevispira</i> A.St.-Hil.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Helicteres cidii</i> Cristóbal.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Helicteres corylifolia</i> Nees & Mart.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Helicteres eitenii</i> Leane	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Palm Grove
<i>Melochia pyramidata</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Mollia lepidota</i> Spruce ex Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Pachira aquatica</i> Aubl.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Anthropic Area, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Pavonia malacophylla</i> (Link & Otto) Garcke	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Peltaea macedoi</i> Krapov. & Cristóbal	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Pseudobombax marginatum</i> (A.St.-Hil., Juss. & Cambess.) A.Robyns	tree	LC	Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Sida glocimari</i> Krapov.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Sida santaremensis</i> Mont.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area

<i>Sterculia striata</i> A.St.-Hil. & Naudin	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Triumfetta bartramia</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Urena lobata</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Restinga
<i>Waltheria indica</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Waltheria operculata</i> Rose	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
Marantaceae				
<i>Goepertia annae</i> (H. Kenn. & J.M.A. Braga) Borchs. & S. Suárez.	herb	NE	Mata Atlântica	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Hylaeanthus hexantha</i> (Poepp. & Endl.) Jonker & A.M.E.Jonker	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Koernickanthus orbiculata</i> (Körn.) L.Andersson	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest

<i>Maranta incrassata</i> L.Andersson.	herb	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Maranta parvifolia</i> Petersen	herb	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Maranta ruiziana</i> Körn.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Monotagma plurispicatum</i> (Körn.) K.Schum.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campinarana, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Myrosma cannifolia</i> L.f.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campinarana, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Melastomataceae				
<i>Aciotis annua</i> (Mart. ex DC.) Triana	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest
<i>Clidemia capitellata</i> (Bonpl.) D. Don	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Clidemia hirta</i> (L.) D.Don	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

<i>Desmoscelis villosa</i> (Aubl.) Naudin	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Henriettea ovata</i> (Cogn.) Penneys, F.A. Michelangeli, Judd et Almeida	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Miconia albicans</i> (Sw.) Triana	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Miconia chamissois</i> Naudin	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Miconia ciliata</i> (Rich.) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Miconia cuspidata</i> Naudin	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Miconia dodecandra</i> Cogn.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest
<i>Miconia elegans</i> Cogn.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Miconia fallax</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Miconia ferruginata</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Miconia heliotropoides</i> Triana	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest
<i>Miconia macrothyrsa</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna

<i>Miconia minutiflora</i> (Bonpl.) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Miconia nervosa</i> (Sm.) Triana	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Miconia prasina</i> (Sw.) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Mouriri pusa</i> Gardner	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Pleroma candolleianum</i> (Mart. ex DC.) Triana	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Riparian Forest
<i>Rhynchanthera cordata</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Rhynchanthera hispida</i> Naudin	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Rhynchanthera novemnervia</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Tibouchina barbiger</i> a (Naudin) Baill.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Tibouchina verticillaris</i> Cogn.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Tococa nitens</i> (Benth.) Triana	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Amazonian Savanna
Meliaceae				
<i>Cedrela fissilis</i> Vell.	tree	VU	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Carapa guianensis</i> Aubl	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Guarea guidonia</i> (L.) Sleumer	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Guarea kunthiana</i> A. Juss.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Guarea macrophylla</i> Vahl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Trichilia elegans</i> A.Juss.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Trichilia pallida</i> Sw.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Menispermaceae				
<i>Abuta grandifolia</i> (Mart.) Sandwith	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
Metteniusaceae				
<i>Emmotum nitens</i> (Benth.) Miers	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
Microteaceae				
<i>Microtea maypurensis</i> (Kunth) G.Don.	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)

Molluginaceae				
<i>Glinus radiatus</i> (Ruiz & Pav.) Rohrb.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea
Moraceae				
<i>Brosimum gaudichaudii</i> Trécul.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Dorstenia brasiliensis</i> Lam.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Dorstenia heringeri</i> Carauta & C. Valente	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Dorstenia tubicina</i> Ruiz & Pav.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Ficus americana</i>	tree	NE	Amazônia	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Ficus obtusiuscula</i> (Miq.) Miq.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Helicostylis tomentosa</i> (Poepp. & Endl.) Rusby	tree	LC	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
Myristicaceae				
<i>Virola sebifera</i> Aubl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Virola surinamensis</i> (Rol. ex Rottb.) Warb.	tree	VU	Amazônia	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
Myrtaceae				

<i>Eugenia biflora</i> (L.) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Eugenia caducibracteata</i> Mazine	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest
<i>Eugenia candolleana</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Eugenia cupulata</i> Amshoff	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Eugenia dysenterica</i> (Mart.) DC.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Eugenia flavescens</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Eugenia ischnosceles</i> O. Berg	tree	NE	Mata Atlântica	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Eugenia mikanioides</i> O. Berg	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Eugenia patrisii</i> Vahl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Varzea Forest
<i>Eugenia polystachya</i> Rich.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Eugenia pseudopsidium</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Eugenia puniceifolia</i> (Kunth) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Eugenia sparsa</i> S.Moore.	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Eugenia stictopetala</i> Mart. ex DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Myrcia excoriata</i> (Mart.) E.Lucas & C.E.Wilson	tree	NE	Mata Atlântica	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Myrcia guianensis</i> (Aubl.) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous

<i>Myrcia multiflora</i> (Lam.) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga Anthropic Area, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Myrcia splendens</i> (Sw.) DC.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Myrcia sylvatica</i> (G.Mey.) DC.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Myrcia tomentosa</i> (Aubl.) DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Myrcia variabilis</i> DC.	shrub	LC	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Myrciaria dubia</i> (Kunth) McVaugh	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Varzea Forest
<i>Psidium acutangulum</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Varzea Forest
<i>Psidium guyanense</i> Pers.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Psidium hians</i> Mart. ex DC.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Psidium myrsinites</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
Nyctaginaceae				
<i>Boerhavia coccinea</i> Mill.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area
Nymphaeaceae				

<i>Nymphaea gardneriana</i> Planch.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Nymphaea tenerinervia</i> Casp.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Aquatic Vegetation
Ochnaceae				
<i>Ouratea castaneifolia</i> (DC.) Engl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Ouratea cearensis</i> (Tiegh.) Sastre & Offroy	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Ouratea ferruginea</i> Engl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Ouratea hexasperma</i> (A.St.-Hil.) Baill.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Ouratea parvifolia</i> (A.St.-Hil.) Engl.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Ouratea riedeliana</i> Engl.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Sauvagesia erecta</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
Oleaceae				
<i>Priogymnanthus hasslerianus</i> (Chodat) P. S. Green.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Onagraceae				
<i>Ludwigia inclinata</i> (L.f.) M.Gómez	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Aquatic Vegetation
Opiliaceae				

<i>Agonandra brasiliensis</i> Miers ex Benth. & Hook.f.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Orchidaceae				
<i>Catasetum barbatum</i> (Lindl.) Lindl.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Manguezal, Palm Grove, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Catasetum confusum</i> G.A.Romero	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Encyclia linearifolioides</i> (Kraenzl.) Hoehne	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga
<i>Eulophia alta</i> (L.) Fawc. & Rendle	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Galeandra montana</i> Barb.Rodr.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Habenaria cryptophila</i> Barb.Rodr.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Oeceoclades maculata</i> (Lindl.) Lindl.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga
<i>Trichocentrum cepula</i> (Hoffmanns.) J.M.H.Shaw	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest

<i>Vanilla palmarum</i> (Salzm. ex Lindl.) Lindl.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
Orobanchaceae				
<i>Esterhazyia macrodonta</i> (Cham.) Benth.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Esterhazyia splendida</i> J.C. Mikan	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Oxalidaceae				
<i>Oxalis divaricata</i> Mart. ex Zucc.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Oxalis hedysarifolia</i> Raddi.	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Oxalis nigrescens</i> A.St.-Hil.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
Passifloraceae				
<i>Passiflora acuminata</i> DC.	climber	NE	Amazônia	Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Passiflora coccinea</i> Aubl.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga	Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Passiflora edulis</i> Sims	climber	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga
<i>Passiflora foetida</i> L.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Passiflora laurifolia</i> L.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Passiflora mansoi</i> (Mart.) Mast.	climber	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Passiflora nitida</i> Kunth	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Passiflora porophylla</i> Vell.	climber	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
Phyllanthaceae				
<i>Amanoa guianensis</i> Aubl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Margaritaria nobilis</i> L.f.	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Phyllanthus caroliniensis</i> Walter	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Phyllanthus juglandifolius</i> Willd.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Phyllanthus orbiculatus</i> Rich.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Phyllanthus urinaria</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Phytolaccaceae				
<i>Microtea celosioides</i> Moq. ex Sennikov & Sukhor.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Microtea maypurensis</i> (Kunth) G.Don.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
Picramniaceae				
<i>Picramnia latifolia</i> Tul.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Palm Grove
Picrodendraceae				
<i>Piranhea trifoliata</i> Baill.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Piperaceae				
<i>Piperomia pellucida</i> (L.) Kunth	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Piper arboreum</i> Aubl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Rupestre, Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Piper dilatatum</i> Rich.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Piper marginatum</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Piper nematanthera</i> C.D.C.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Piper schottii</i> (Miq.) C.D.C.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Piper tuberculatum</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Plantaginaceae				

<i>Scoparia dulcis</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Stemodia foliosa</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Restinga
Poaceae				
<i>Aristida longifolia</i> Trin.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Aristida riparia</i> Trin.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Aristida setifolia</i> Kunth.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Axonopus aureus</i> P. Beauv.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Palm Grove, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Axonopus capillaris</i> (Lam.) Chase	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Axonopus complanatus</i> (Nees) Dedecca	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna

<i>Axonopus polydactylus</i> (Steud.) Dedecca.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Axonopus pressus</i> (Nees ex Steud.) Parodi.	herb	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Axonopus purpusii</i> (Mez) Chase	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Axonopus siccus</i> (Nees) Kuhlman.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Riparian Forest, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Axonopus singularis</i> (Swallen) Alicia López & Morrone.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Bouteloua americana</i> (L.) Scribn.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Willd.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area
<i>Digitaria fragilis</i> (Steud.) Lucas.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Digitaria violascens</i> Link	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Aquatic Vegetation

<i>Eragrostis hypnoides</i> (Lam.) Britton, Sterns & Poggenb.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Campo de Várzea
<i>Eragrostis maypurensis</i> (Kunth) Steud.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Gymnopogon foliosus</i> (Willd.) Nees	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Hiladea tenuis</i> (J. Presl & C. Presl) C. Silva & R.P. Oliveira	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Ichnanthus calvescens</i> (Nees ex Trin.) Döll	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Ichnanthus hoffmannseggii</i> (Roem. & Schult.) Döll	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Ichnanthus inconstans</i> (Trin. ex Nees) Döll	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Ichnanthus oplismenoides</i> Munro ex Döll.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea
<i>Leptochloa virgata</i> (L.) P.Beauv.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Mesosetum annuum</i> Swallen	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Mesosetum cayennense</i> Steud.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Mesosetum loliiforme</i> (Hochst.) Chase	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Mnesithea granularis</i> (L.) de Koning & Sosef.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Ocellochloa stolonifera</i> (Poir.) Zuloaga & Morrone	herb	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Campinarana, Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Oedochloa procurrens</i> (Nees ex Trin.) C.Silva & R.P.Oliveira.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Pantanal	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Olyra ciliatifolia</i> Raddi	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Panicum dichotomiflorum</i> Michx.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Igapó Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Panicum exiguum</i> Mez.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Paspalum atratum</i> Swallen	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Paspalum carinatum</i> Humb. & Bonpl. ex Flüggé.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Paspalum ceresia</i> (Kuntze) Chase	herb		Não consta no Flora	

<i>Paspalum clavuliferum</i> C.Wright.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> P.J.Bergius	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest
<i>Paspalum expansum</i> Döll	herb	NE	Cerrado	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal
<i>Paspalum foveolatum</i> Steud.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Paspalum gardnerianum</i> Ness	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Paspalum lanciflorum</i> Nees ex Steud.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Paspalum macranthecium</i> Parodi.	herb	NE	Cerrado, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Paspalum marmoratum</i> Kuhlmann.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Paspalum melanospermum</i> Desv. ex Poir.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Manguezal, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Paspalum multicaule</i> Poir.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Paspalum paniculatum</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Paspalum plicatulum</i> Michx.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest

				(Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Paspalum subsesquiglume</i> Döll	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Paspalum vexillarium</i> G.H.Rua et al.	herb	NE	Cerrado	Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Paspalum virgatum</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea
<i>Rugolosa pilosa</i> (Sw.) Zuloaga	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Setaria parviflora</i> (Poir.) Kerguelen	herb	CR	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Sporobolus indicus</i> (L.) R.Br.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Steinchisma decipiens</i> (Nees ex Trin.) W.V.Br.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Steinchisma laxum</i> (Sw.) Zuloaga	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Steinchisma spathellosum</i> (Döll) Renvoize	herb	NE	Mata Atlântica	Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Streptostachys asperifolia</i> Desv.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu),

<i>Taquara micrantha</i> (Kunth) Davidse & Zuloaga	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation Campo Rupestre, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Trachypogon spicatus</i> (L.f.) Kuntze.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
Polygalaceae				
<i>Asemeia violacea</i> (Aubl.) J.F.B.Pastore & J.R.Abbott	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Bredemeyera floribunda</i> Willd.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Caamembeca spectabilis</i> (DC.) J.F.B.Pastore	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Mata Atlântica	Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Moutabea excoriata</i> Mart. ex Miq.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Polygala longicaulis</i> Kunth	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Polygonaceae				
<i>Coccoloba coronata</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Coccoloba latifolia</i> Lam.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga

<i>Coccoloba lucidula</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Coccoloba mollis</i> Casar.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Portulacaceae				
<i>Portulaca mucronata</i> Link	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Portulaca sedifolia</i> N.E.Br.	herb	NE	Amazônia	Anthropic Area, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Primulaceae				
<i>Clavija lancifolia</i> Desf.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest
<i>Cybianthus detergens</i> Mart.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Cybianthus gardneri</i> (A.DC.) G.Agostini	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Cybianthus glaber</i> A.DC.	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Geissanthus ambiguus</i> (Mart.) G.Agostini	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
Proteaceae				
<i>Euplassa inaequalis</i> (Pohl) Engl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga

<i>Roupala montana</i> Aubl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Rhamnaceae				
<i>Gouania latifolia</i> Reissek	climber	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Gouania velutina</i> Reissek	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Rhamnidium elaeocarpum</i> Reissek.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Rubiaceae				
<i>Alibertia edulis</i> (Rich.) A.Rich.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Augusta longifolia</i> (Spreng.) Rehder	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest
<i>Borreria latifolia</i> (Aubl.) K.Schum.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Borreria spinosa</i> Cham. et Schltldl.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Borreria verticillata</i> (L.) G.Mey.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Chiococca alba</i> (L.) Hitchc.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Chomelia obtusa</i> Cham. & Schltl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo Limpo, Riparian Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest
<i>Chomelia ribesoides</i> Benth. ex A.Gray	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Cordia concolor</i> (Cham.) K.Schum.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Cordia elliptica</i> (Cham.) Kuntze	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Cordia macrophylla</i> (K.Schum.) Kuntze	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Cordia myrciifolia</i> (K.Schum.) C.H.Perss. & Delprete	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Cordia rigida</i> (K.Schum.) Kuntze	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

<i>Cordia triflora</i> A.Rich. ex DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Pantanal	Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Coussarea hydrangeifolia</i> (Benth.) Müll.Arg.	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Coussarea platyphylla</i> Müll.Arg.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Palm Grove
<i>Declieuxia fruticosa</i> (Willd. ex Roem. & Schult.) Kuntze	shrub	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Dialypetalanthus fuscescens</i> Kuhlm.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Emmeorrhiza umbellata</i> (Spreng.) Schm.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Faramea bracteata</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest
<i>Faramea multiflora</i> A.Rich. ex DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Faramea nitida</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga
<i>Ferdinandusa elliptica</i> (Pohl) Pohl	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest
<i>Gonzalagunia dicocca</i> Cham. & Schltdl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest
<i>Guettarda pohliana</i> Müll.Arg.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest

<i>Guettarda spruceana</i> Müll.Arg.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest
<i>Guettarda viburnoides</i> Cham. & Schltld.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Hexasepalum teres</i> (Walter) J.H.Kirkbr.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Machaonia acuminata</i> Bonpl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Malanea macrophylla</i> Bartl. ex Griseb.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Oldenlandia lancifolia</i> (Schumach.) DC.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Pagamea guianensis</i> Aubl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Carrasco, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Palicourea hoffmannseggiana</i> (Schult.) Borhidi.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Carrasco, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest
<i>Palicourea marcgravii</i> A.St.-Hil.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Palicourea racemosa</i> Rich.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Perama hirsuta</i> Aubl.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Psychotria carthagenensis</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Campo de Várzea, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Psychotria pedunculosa</i> Rich.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Randia armata</i> (Sw.) DC.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Richardia grandiflora</i> (Cham. & Schltl.) Steud.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Rosenbergiodendron longiflorum</i> (Ruiz & Pav.) Fagerl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Rudgea erioloba</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Cerrado	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Rudgea longiflora</i> Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest
<i>Rudgea viburnoides</i> (Cham.) Benth.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Sipanea hispida</i> Benth. ex Wernham	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Stachyarrhena harleyi</i> J.H.Kirkbr.	shrub	NE	Mata Atlântica	Restinga

<i>Staelia virgata</i> (Link ex Roem. & Schult.) K.Schum.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Palm Grove, Aquatic Vegetation
<i>Tocoyena brasiliensis</i> Mart.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Tocoyena formosa</i> (Cham. & Schltdl.) K.Schum.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Tocoyena neglecta</i> N.E.Br.	shrub	NE	Amazônia	Campinarana, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Uncaria guianensis</i> (Aubl.) J.F.Gmel.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Rutaceae				
<i>Zanthoxylum rhoifolium</i> Lam.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Zanthoxylum riedelianum</i> Engl.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Salicaceae				

<i>Banara guianensis</i> Aubl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Allophylus strictus</i> Radlk.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Casearia aculeata</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Casearia commersoniana</i> Cambess.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Casearia gossypiosperma</i> Briq.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Casearia grandiflora</i> Cambess	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Casearia javitensis</i> Kunth	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Santalaceae				
<i>Cupania vernalis</i> Cambess.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Homalium guianense</i> (Aubl.) Oken	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
Sapindaceae				

<i>Magonia pubescens</i> A.St.-Hil.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Matayba guianensis</i> Aubl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Paullinia pinnata</i> L.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Manguezal, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Phoradendron bathoryctum</i> Eichler.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Manguezal, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Phoradendron quadrangulare</i> (Kunth) Griseb	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Manguezal, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Phoradendron strongyloclados</i> Eichler.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Amazonian Savanna
<i>Pseudima frutescens</i> (Aubl.) Radlk.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Sapindus saponaria</i> L.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Serjania reticulata</i> Cambess.	climber	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Toulicia reticulata</i> Radlk.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
Sapotaceae				
<i>Chrysophyllum marginatum</i> (Hook. & Arn.) Radlk.	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest
<i>Chrysophyllum sparsiflorum</i> Klotzsch ex Miq.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest
<i>Micropholis casiquiarensis</i> Aubrév.	tree	LC	Amazônia	Terra Firme Forest
<i>Micropholis gardneriana</i> (A.DC.) Pierre.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Pouteria gardneri</i> (Mart. & Miq.) Baehni	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Pouteria glomerata</i> (Miq.) Radlk.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Carrasco, Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Pouteria macrophylla</i> (Lam.) Eyma	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest)

<i>Pouteria ramiflora</i> (Mart.) Radlk.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga
<i>Pradosia surinamensis</i> (Eyma) T.D.Penn.	tree	NE	Amazônia	Campinarana, Terra Firme Forest
Simaroubaceae				
<i>Homalolepis ferruginea</i> (A.St.-Hil.) Devecchi & Pirani.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
Siparunaceae				
<i>Siparuna brasiliensis</i> (Spreng.) A.DC.	shrub	LC	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Siparuna guianensis</i> Aubl.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Siparuna reginae</i> (Tul.) A.DC.	tree	LC	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Smilacaceae				
<i>Smilax fluminensis</i> Steud.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Solanaceae				
<i>Physalis angulata</i> L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area
<i>Schwenckia americana</i> Rooyen ex L.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area

<i>Solanum asperum</i> Rich.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Solanum crinitum</i> Lam.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Solanum grandiflorum</i> Dun	shrub	NE	Não ocorre no Brasil	
<i>Solanum lycocarpum</i> A.St.-Hil.	shrub	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Solanum rhytidoandrum</i> Sendtn.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Solanum stramonifolium</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
<i>Solanum subinerme</i> Jacq.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest
Trigoniaceae				
<i>Trigonia nivea</i> Cambess.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna
Turneraceae				
<i>Piriqueta cistoides</i> (L.) Griseb.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

<i>Turnera coerulea</i> DC.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Turnera melochioides</i> Cambess.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Turnera odorata</i> Rich.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Turnera subulata</i> Sm.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Cerrado (lato sensu), Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Ulmaceae				
<i>Trema micrantha</i> (L.) Blume	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Urticaceae				
<i>Cecropia concolor</i> Willd.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Anthropic Area, Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest
<i>Cecropia pachystachya</i> Trécul.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga
Verbenaceae				

<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Lantana fucata</i> Lindl.	shrub	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophyllous Forest, Restinga
<i>Lippia organoides</i> Kunth	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	herb	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Altitude Field, Riparian Forest
<i>Stachytarpheta cayennensis</i> (Rich.) Vahl.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Stachytarpheta indica</i> (L.) Vahl	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophyllous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Stachytarpheta sessilis</i> Moldenke.	herb	NE	Caatinga	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu)

<i>Vitex polygama</i> Cham.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
Violaceae				
<i>Pombalia calceolaria</i> (L.) Paula-Souza	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
<i>Rinorea ovalifolia</i> (Britton) S.F. Blake	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Pantanal	Terra Firme Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Vitaceae				
<i>Cissus erosa</i> Rich.	shrub	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campinarana, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Cissus spinosa</i> Cambess.	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Varzea Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Palm Grove
<i>Cissus subrhomboidea</i> (Baker) Planch.	climber	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation

<i>Cissus verticillata</i> (L.) Nicolson & C.E.Jarvis	climber	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Caatinga (stricto sensu), Altitude Field, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Igapó Forest, Terra Firme Forest, Varzea Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Evergreen Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Palm Grove, Restinga, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Clematicissus simsiana</i> (Schult. & Schult.f.) Lombardi.	climber	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Deciduous Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Restinga
Vochysiaceae				
<i>Callisthene fasciculata</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest
<i>Callisthene minor</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado	Carrasco, Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Qualea grandiflora</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Qualea parviflora</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Cerrado (lato sensu), Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Salvertia convallariodora</i> A. St.-Hil.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu), Amazonian Savanna
<i>Vochysia gardneri</i> Warm.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)
<i>Vochysia haenkeana</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Amazônia, Cerrado	Varzea Forest
<i>Vochysia pyramidalis</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Riparian Forest
<i>Vochysia rufa</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Cerrado	Cerrado (lato sensu)

<i>Vochysia tucanorum</i> Mart.	tree	NE	Cerrado, Mata Atlântica	Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest)
Xyridaceae				
<i>Xyris savanensis</i> Miq.	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pantanal	Caatinga (stricto sensu), Campinarana, Altitude Field, Campo de Várzea, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Restinga, Amazonian Savanna, Aquatic Vegetation, Rocky Outcrop Vegetation
<i>Xyris schizachne</i> Mart.	herb	NE	Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa	Altitude Field, Campo Limpo, Campo Rupestre, Cerrado (lato sensu), Aquatic Vegetation
Zingiberaceae				
<i>Hedychium coronarium</i> J.Koenig	herb	NE	Amazônia, Caatinga, Cerrado, Mata Atlântica, Pampa, Pantanal	Anthropic Area, Campo de Várzea, Cerrado (lato sensu), Riparian Forest, Seasonal Semideciduous Forest, Ombrophylous Forest (Rainforest), Mixed Ombrophylous Forest, Restinga